

NOTES

Biological activity: Compounds 1–5 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity by ditch-plate technique³ using concentration levels 2 and 5 mg ml⁻¹. The test organisms employed were *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Compounds 1, 2 and 4 showed activity against *S. typhi* at 2 mg ml⁻¹ and *S. aureus* at 5 mg ml⁻¹. At 5 mg ml⁻¹ concentration level, compounds 2, 5 showed activity against *E. coli* and 3, 4 showed activity towards *B. subtilis*.

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Analysis of the Essential Fatty Acid rich Seed Oils

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IN the present investigation we have analysed seed oils of six indigenous species: *Sesbania aculeata*, *S. grandiflora*, *S. aegyptica*, *Robinia pseudoacacia* (all Fam: Papilionaceae), *Albizia moluccana* (Fam: Mimosae) and *Pinus roxburghii* (Fam: Pinaceae).

Experimental

The seed samples (purchased from Pratap Nursery, Dehradun) were powdered and extracted with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). Analytical values were determined according to the recommended procedure¹. The methyl esters were prepared by the usual method (CH₃OH/H⁺)². Tlc (silica gel G, 0.25 mm; petroleum ether-Et₂O-HOAc=80:20:1, v/v/v; detection: charring with 20% aqueous HClO₄, ir spectra (Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer), uv spectra (MeOH; Beckman DK2A spectrophotometer) and glc of methyl esters (Perkin-Elmer F-11 model, DEGS 15% on chromosorb W 45–60 mesh) were performed. In general, oils and methyl esters were examined by various qualitative tests, picric acid test for epoxy group, DNP test for keto group and Halphen test for cyclopropene moiety^{3,4} to ascertain the presence or absence of the unusual acids.

Results and Discussion

The uv and ir spectral analyses of seed oils showed no conjugation, *trans*-unsaturation or any unusual functional groups. The analytical characteristics and the fatty acid compositions of the six seed oils are given in Table 1. The oil content varied from 2.8 to 23% and the percentage of saturated acids ranged from 11.54 to 35.78%.

The results show that *S. aculeata* and *P. roxburghii* seeds are rich in oil with high linoleic acid and PUFA contents. Thus, after some modifications, these two oils can play important nutritional role. The remaining four species are also the rich sources of PUFA, but their main drawback is that their oil content is very low. *S. grandiflora* and *S. aegyptica* seed oils resemble remarkably with soybean oil and maize oil, based on their linoleic acid content. All the seed oils resemble the general pattern of oleic-linoleic type.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITIONS OF SEED OILS*

Sl. no.	Characteristics	<i>S. ac</i>	<i>S. gr</i>	<i>S. ae</i>	<i>A. mo</i>	<i>R. ps</i>	<i>P. ro</i>
1.	Oil content (%)	23.0	8.5	3.5	2.8	6.7	22.4
2.	Iodine value	193.4	116.5	115.9	193.5	188.2	192.7
3.	Sap. value	130.6	194.7	193.9	145.4	110.4	103.2
4.	Ref. index [η] _D ²⁰	1.4867	1.4892	1.4829	1.4857	1.4892	1.4845
5.	Methyl ester composition (wt %)						
	16:0	10.29	13.77	14.12	12.50	6.85	4.67
	18:0	3.58	1.83	6.77	—	—	—
	18:1	11.63	26.57	14.12	18.75	4.11	26.93
	18:2	68.03	51.07	58.19	30.28	60.00	49.54
	18:3	2.05	1.22	—	28.58	—	11.54
	20:0	2.68	3.67	6.72	3.12	17.28	1.79
	22:0	1.07	—	—	4.50	11.65	4.19
	24:0	—	1.83	—	2.33	—	0.89
	PUFA	70.08	52.29	58.19	58.86	60.00	61.08

**S. ac*=*S. aculeata*; *S. gr*=*S. grandiflora*; *S. ae*=*S. aegyptica*; *A. mo*=*A. moluccana*; *R. ps*=*R. pseudoacacia*; *P. ro*=*P. roxburghii*.

Earlier, fatty acid compositions of *S. grandiflora*⁵ and *S. aegyptica*⁶ were determined by fractionation methods. It is found that the present observations are different from the previous one.

Acknowledgement

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Fatty Acid Composition and Characteristics of *Cassia glauca* Seed Oil

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CASSIA glauca (N.O. Leguminosae) plant occur throughout India. No work has been reported so far on fixed oil from its seeds. Phytochemical screening of forest seed oils is a subject of intensive research to explore new alternative sources for conventional oils. It was therefore considered worthwhile to isolate the fixed oil from the seeds of *C. glauca* (collected locally) using glc technique.

Experimental

Cleaned and dried seeds (2 kg) were crushed and extracted exhaustively with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). Removal of the solvent yielded a yellowish oil with a faint odour, which was purified through animal charcoal and Fuller's earth. The oil was subjected to various qualitative tests, e.g. picric acid test¹ for epoxy group and Halphen test² for cyclopropene moiety. The characteristics of the purified oil determined according to standard AOCS³ methods are given in the Table 1. The mixed fatty acids were converted to their methyl esters⁴. Glc of the methyl esters was carried out on a CIC gas chromatograph equipped with flame ionisation detector using stainless steel column (3 mm x 2 m) packed with 20% DEGS on chromosorb and using

nitrogen as carrier gas. The injection port, columns and flame ionisation detector block were maintained at 260, 190 and 190° respectively. The methyl esters were identified⁵ by co-glc with authentic samples.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE OIL

Yield of oil (%)	5
Specific gravity (at 30°)	0.916
Refractive index (at 40°)	1.468
Moisture content (%)	3.9
Acid value	1.8
Saponification value	192
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	4.12
Iodine value (Wijs method)	96.2
Fatty acids (%)	
Palmitic	30.354 3
Stearic	1.317 6
Oleic	23.497 9
Linoleic	42.916 9
Linolenic	1.627 1
Arachidic	0.286 2

Results and Discussion

The results gave no indication of conjugation or *trans*-unsaturation or any other functional groups in the oil. No epoxy function could be detected in it. The oil is of non-drying type and indicates its potential for edible use after due processing. However, the seeds cannot be a good source of oil to be exploited economically.

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Synthesis of new 3-Substituted-*s*-triazolo-[3,4-*b*]-8-methylpyrazolo[3',4'-*e*](5*H*)-[1,3,4]thiadiazines

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new *s*-triazolothiadiazines as potential anthelmintic agents^{1,2,3}, the hitherto unreported title compounds (3) have been prepared by the condensation of the corresponding 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,